

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The influence of directive leadership style and work motivation on employee performance with career development as an intervening variable at PT Hutama Karya Infrastructure for Pekanbaru-Padang Toll Road Development, Padang Siring Section

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the Influence of Directive Leadership Style and Work Motivation on Employee Performance with Career Development as an Intervening Variable at PT Hutama Karya Infrastructure for the Construction of the Pekanbaru-Padang Toll Road, Padang Sicincin Section. This research is a quantitative research. The population in this study is all employees of PT Hutama Karya Infrastruktur Pembangunan Tol Pekanbaru-Padang, Padang Siring Section which totals 259 employees. The sampling technique used was purposive random sampling using the slovin formula so that the number of samples was 79 respondents. The data used are primary data obtained from observations and interviews, and secondary data obtained from documentation, books and scientific journals. The analysis method used in this study is the path analysis method (Path Analysis) to see the direct and indirect influence between variables. The results of this study show that the variable Directive leadership style has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees of PT Hutama Karya Infrastruktur Pekanbaru-Padang Toll Road Development, Padang Sicincin Section. The directive leadership style has a positive and significant effect on the career development of employees of PT Hutama Karya Infrastruktur Pekanbaru-Padang Toll Road Development, Padang Sicincin Section. Motivation has a positive and but not significant effect on the performance of employees of PT Hutama Karya Infrastruktur Pekanbaru-Padang Toll Road Development, Padang Sicincin. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on the career development of employees of PT Hutama Karya Infrastruktur Pekanbaru-Padang Toll Road Development, Padang Sicinring Section. Employee career development does not have a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees of PT Hutama Karya Infrastruktur Pekanbaru-Padang Toll Road Development, Padang Sicincin Section. Employee Career Development does not play a role in mediating the influence of motivation on the performance of employees of PT Hutama Karya Infrastruktur Pekanbaru-Padang Toll Road Development, Padang Sicincin Section. Employee Career Development plays a role in mediating the influence of directive leadership style on employee performance of PT Hutama Karya Infrastruktur Pekanbaru-Padang Toll Road Development, Padang Sicincin Section.

Keywords: Directive Leadership Style; Directive Leadership Style Indicator; Work Motivation; Work Motivation Indicators; Career Development; Career Development Indicators; Employee Performance; Employee Performance Indicators

1. Introduction

In the era of globalization, companies compete in an increasingly competitive global market. Globalization brings rapid and complex changes in various aspects of business, including technology, regulation, and consumer needs. Competent and qualified human resources can help companies face global competition by providing competitive advantage through innovation, productivity, and better customer service. The position of human resources is not only as a means of

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production, but also as a driver and determinant of the production process and all organizational activities. Therefore, HR must be managed properly to increase the effectiveness and efficiency of the organization.

Employee performance is a critical factor that can affect the success and sustainability of an organization. With good performance, every employee can solve all organizational burdens effectively and efficiently so that problems that occur in the organization can be resolved properly. As stated by Afandi (2018) that performance is the result of work that can be achieved by a person or group of people in a company in accordance with their respective authorities and responsibilities in an effort to achieve organizational goals illegally, does not violate the law and does not conflict with morals and ethics. The achievement of the goals of an organization is the main focus of the formation of the organization. To achieve these organizational goals, a leader who is able to work effectively is needed. The smarter the leader in carrying out his role, of course, the faster the company's goals will be achieved.

Leaders within the organization have an important role in influencing employee performance through the leadership style applied. Leadership style is a pattern of behavior of a person to motivate others so that they want to work together to achieve goals. A leader must have and demonstrate a leadership style. According to House & Mitchell, (1974); Indvik (1987) has 4 path-goal leadership styles that serve to provide structure and/or reward to subordinates are directive, supportive, participatory, and achievement-oriented. Leaders can direct their teams (Leader Directiveness), Leaders can support their teams (Leader Supportiveness), Leaders play an active role in the team (Participative Leadership), Achievement-Oriented Leadership.

The leadership style used in this study is directive leadership style. Robbins (2015) states that the leadership directive tells subordinates what is expected of them, gives specific guidelines, asks subordinates to follow demanding rules and coordinates their work. The function of directive leaders is to provide task structure by planning, organizing, coordinating, directing, and controlling the work of their subordinates. The directive leadership style is characterized by a leader who provides clear, firm and in-depth direction to his subordinates. Leaders with this style tend to make their own decisions and give specific instructions about the tasks that must be performed by employees. Such a directive attitude is expected to produce positive results

In addition to leadership style, work motivation factors also have a significant influence on employee performance. Work motivation is an internal factor that drives individuals to achieve goals and give their best effort in work. Motivated employees have a tendency to perform better and be more productive. According to Afandi (2018) motivation is a desire that arises from within a person or individual because they are inspired, encouraged, and driven to carry out activities with sincerity, pleasure, and earnestness so that the results of the activities they do get good and quality results.

Furthermore, career development is also an important aspect in improving employee performance. Career development involves providing opportunities and developing the capabilities of employees so that they can grow and improve their competencies. With career development opportunities, employees feel supported and have clear goals, which can motivate them to improve their performance and reach their best potential. Career development within organizations includes efforts to improve the skills, knowledge, and abilities of employees so that they can achieve advancement in their careers. Career development can increase work motivation because employees feel valued and have better career prospects, which in turn can affect their performance.

Director of PT Hutama Karya Infrastruktur (Persero) Pekanbaru-Padang toll road construction division, Padang Siring Section reported the progress of the construction of the Padang-Pekanbaru Toll Road, which is a corridor connecting the Trans Sumatra Toll Road (JTTS) network. The construction of the toll road which is divided into 6 sections will connect the connectivity of West Sumatra and Riau provinces with a total length of 254 kilometers (km). Thus, good employee performance at PT HKI is not only important for the success of current project work, but also has an impact on the sustainability and growth of the company in the future. Efforts to improve employee performance through support, training, and development will provide long-term benefits to the organization and create a positive and productive work environment.

1.1. Directive Leadership Style

According to Kartono in Paramita (2017), in his book "Leaders and Leadership", states that Leadership is the activity of influencing people so that they want to work together to achieve the desired goals. Robbins (2015) states that the leadership directive tells subordinates what is expected of them, gives specific guidelines, asks subordinates to follow demanding rules and coordinates their work. This type is the practice of authoritarian leadership, members or subordinates never have the opportunity to participate in expressing opinions, let alone in decision-making of this style.

Based on the use of force, power and authority give specific clues to the performance of his subordinates. This type of leader considers his leadership to be his personal right and argues that he determines everything in the organization, without consulting his subordinates who carry it out. The implementation is very tense as well, so it is more appropriate if this type of leadership or leader is used for emergencies, where a consultation with subordinates is no longer possible.

1.2. Directive Leadership Style Indicator

Directive leadership is a leadership behavior in which the leader tells subordinates what is expected of giving instructions on what to do, and shows subordinates how to do the task well. In other words, this kind of leadership provides specific direction on how tasks are accomplished, schedules, rules, and definitive standards that employees must meet. The indicators include Robbins (2015):

- The leader maintains the standard of work appearance of subordinates.
- The leader tells how to complete tasks and set deadlines.
- The leader sets the standard for task completion.

1.3. Work Motivation

The term motivation, in everyday life has a variety of meanings both related to individual behavior and organizational behavior. Motivation is an important element in humans that plays a role in realizing success in human business and work. The basis for the implementation of motivation by a leader is knowledge and attention to the human behavior he leads as a determining factor for organizational success.

Adha (2019) suggests that theoretically motivation is formed because humans have basic needs categories such as physiological needs, security, social, ego, and self-realization. These needs form a hierarchy and each will be active if the lower needs have been met. While Sedarmayanti (2014) said that motivation is the willingness to expend a high level of effort towards organizational goals conditioned by the ability of that effort to meet individual needs.

According to Afandi (2018) motivation is a desire that arises from within a person or individual because they are inspired, encouraged, and encouraged to carry out activities with sincerity, pleasure and earnestness so that the results of the activities carried out get good and quality results.

1.4. Work Motivation Indicators

Work motivation indicators according to Adha (2019) are:

- Physical Needs
- The need for a sense of security.
- Social needs.
- The need for rewards
- The need for encouragement to achieve goals

1.5. Career Development

Career development development is a process of increasing individual work willingness achieved in order to achieve the desired career Affandi (2018). However, of course, the various concepts, aspects, and processes that surround it are not that simple. As expressed by Priansa (2018) who argues that career development is a series of separate work activities is still a complementary relationship, sustainable and provides meaning to employee lives.

Meanwhile, according to Sutrisno (2019), career development is personal improvements made to achieve a career plan. In other words, the company organization or leaders have prepared a plan in advance about how to develop the careers of employees during work.

1.6. Career Development Indicators

In measuring the achievement of a variable, concrete indicators are needed that can be various symptoms or a real action that will affect something, including this career development problem. According to Priansa (2018), career development indicators include the following.

- Career planning
- Career development
- Career Development Supported by HR Department
- The role of feedback on performance

1.7. Employee Performance

According to Kasmir (2018) is the result of performance and work behavior that has been achieved in completing the tasks and responsibilities given in a certain period. Performance refers to the degree of achievement of the tasks that make up the work of all employees. Performance also reflects how well employees meet the requirements of a job that has been determined by the company in accordance with their respective fields of work. Meanwhile, according to Smith in Sedarmayanti (2017) states: *Performance* or performance is: "... *output drive from process human or otherwise*", so it says that performance is the result or output of a process.

According to Sutrisno (2016), performance is a person's success in carrying out tasks, work results that can be achieved by a person or group of people in an organization in accordance with their respective authorities and responsibilities or about how a person is expected to function and behave in accordance with the tasks that have been assigned to him as well as quantity, quality and time used in performing tasks. Supardi (2013) suggests that performance is the result of work that has been achieved by someone in an organization to achieve goals based on standardization or size and time adjusted to the type of work and in accordance with established norms and ethics.

1.8. Employee Performance Indicators

The dimensions and performance indicators used in this study adapt the theory expressed by Kasmir (2018), namely:

- Quality
- Quantity (Quantity)
- Time (time period)
- Cost Reduction
- Supervision
- Relationship between employees

2. Material and methods

This research is a quantitative research that uses the type of associative research with the population which is then used as a research respondent with the object of research, namely all employees at PT Hutama Karya Infrastructure for the Construction of the Pekanbaru-Padang Toll Road, Padang Sicinring Section. The population in this study is all employees of PT Hutama Karya Infrastruktur Pembangunan Jalan Pekanbaru-Padang, Padang Siring Section which amounts to 259 employees, where the number of permanent employees is 99 people and the number of contract employees is 160 people. The determination of the sample in this study used the slovin formula with the sampling technique used was purposive random sampling so that the number of samples was 79 respondents. The data used are primary data obtained from observations and interviews, while secondary data are obtained from documentation, books and scientific journals. The data analysis method used in this study is a path analysis method (Path Analysis) to see the direct and indirect influence between variables.

3. Results and discussion

1.9. Evaluation of the Measurement Model (Outer Model)

1.9.1. Convergent Validity

Convergent validity aims to determine the validity of each relationship between indicators and their latent constructs or variables. In this study, a loading factor limit of the amount of 0.70. If using the standard value of *Convergent Validity* > 0.70, then the loading value below 0.70 is removed from the model.

Figure 1 Model PLS

The results of processing using SmartPLS can be seen in figure 1. The majority of indicators in each variable in this study have a loading value greater than 0.70 except for indicators PK3, PK4, KK2, and KK3 which have a loading value of less than 0.70. This shows that variable indicators that have a loading value of >0.70 are declared valid to meet the criteria. While variable indicators that have a loading value of <0.70 have a low level of validity so that the variable indicators need to be eliminated or removed from the model.

Table 1 Composite Reliability and AVE values

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
GKD	0.858	0.868	0.913	0.778
KK	0.796	0.756	0.819	0.602
MTV	0.786	0.788	0.862	0.609
PK	0.783	0.802	0.901	0.820

Based on table 1 it can be seen that Cronbach's alpha and Composite Reliability values have above 0.70 for the entire construct. Therefore, there are no reliability problems found in the model formed. Similarly, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) of each receipt has a value above 0.50. Thus all constructs meet reliable criteria according to the recommended criteria.

1.10. Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity is done to ensure that each concept of each model is different from other variables. Measurement of discriminant validity using Fornell-Larcker submitted criteria and "crossloadings". The tabeli below shows the discriminant results of the research model by looking at the Fornell-Larcker value.

Table 2 Fornell-Larcker

	GKD	KK	MTV	PK
GKD	0.882			
KK	0.517	0.776		
MTV	0.575	0.448	0.780	
PK	0.476	0.326	0.717	0.906

Table 2. shows that the correlation value of the association construct is higher compared to other constructs so that it can be said that the model has good discriminant validity. In addition to evaluating the value of the fornell-larcker criterion, researchers also consider the value of cross-loading. Cross-loadings is a measure that indicates the outer loadings value of the indicator on the corresponding construct must be greater than the cross-loading value on other constructs. Below are the cross-loading values of each variable construct.

Table 3 Cross Loading

	GKD	KK	MTV	PK
GKD1	0.872	0.537	0.480	0.382
GKD2	0.922	0.452	0.578	0.481
GKD3	0.851	0.364	0.456	0.393
KK1	0.539	0.830	0.435	0.301
KK4	0.324	0.769	0.297	0.338
KK5	0.246	0.725	0.257	0.074
MTV2	0.634	0.294	0.756	0.590
MTV3	0.501	0.351	0.796	0.518
MTV4	0.281	0.343	0.774	0.515
MTV5	0.379	0.404	0.795	0.604
PK1	0.371	0.289	0.577	0.887
PK2	0.482	0.302	0.711	0.924

Based on the test results of cross-loading, it shows that all outer loadings indicator values in the corresponding construct are greater than the cross-loading values in other constructs. It can be concluded that all constructs have good discriminant validity.

1.11. Evaluation of Structural Model (Inner Model)

The inner model is a structural model used to predict causality relationships (cause-and-effect relationships) between latent variables or variables that cannot be measured directly.

1.12. Model-Inner Model Cholinarity Test

Model cholinarity tests are used to show there is no multicollination between variables. The value used by looking at the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value <5.00.

Table 4 Model-Inner Model Cholinarity Test

	GKD	KK	MTV	PK
GKD		1.512		1.493
KK				
MTV		2.404		1.493
PK		2.081		

It can be seen in table 4. That the VIF value of all variable indicators is <5, so that there is no cholinarity between each variable indicator measured.

1.13. R-Square

R-square is a measure of the proportion of variation in the value of an affected variable (endogenous) that can be explained by the variable affecting it (exogenous) by criteria:

R2 value = 0.75 ☐ Substantial (large/strong) R2 value = 0.50 ☐ Moderate R2 value = 0.25 ☐ Weak (small)

Table 5 R-Square

	R-square	R-square adjusted
KK	0.302	0.274
PK	0.519	0.507

In table 5. It can be seen that R-Square Model Line I = 0.519, meaning that the ability of GKD and MTV variables to explain PK is 51.9%. And R-Square Model Line II = 0.302, meaning that the ability of GKD and MTV through PK in explaining KK is 30.2%.

1.14. F-Square

F-Square is a measure used to assess the relative impact of an influencing variable (exogenous) on the affected variable (endogenous). By criteria:

If F=0.02 ☐ Small/bad If F=0.15 ☐ Medium

If F=0.35 ☐ Large/Good

Table 6 F-Square

	GKD	KK	MTV	PK
GKD		0.145		0.130
KK				
MTV		0.138		0.610
PK		0.155		

Based on table 6, it can be concluded as follows:

- Effect of GKD ☐ PK = 0.130 (medium)
- Effect of MTV ☐ PK = 0.610 (big/good)
- Effect of GKD ☐ KK = 0.145 (medium)
- Effect of MTV ☐ KK = 0.138 (medium)
- Effect PK ☐ KK = 0.155 = (medium)

1.15. Test the hypothesis

The significance test can be determined by looking at the t-statistical value and the p-value of whether a hypothesis is accepted or rejected. Hypothesis testing is carried out by looking at the criteria of t-statistical values and probability values, using statistical values >0.164 and p-values <0.05. Test the hypothesis of this study using a one-tailed test so that the hypothesis is declared accepted if the value of t-statistics >1.64 with p-values <0.05.

Table 7 Path Coefficient

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
GKD -> KK	0.391	0.395	0.142	2.753	0.006
GKD -> PK	0.195	0.086	0.116	0.820	0.012
MTV -> KK	0.252	0.272	0.212	1.191	0.234
MTV-> PK	0.662	0.676	0.108	6.129	0.000
PK -> KK	-0.041	-0.056	0.187	0.218	0.827

Based on the test results of path coefficients that:

- Directive leadership style has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with a path coefficient of 0.391 and a p-value of 0.006.
- The directive leadership style has a positive and significant effect on the career development of employees with a path coefficient of 0.195 and a p-value of 0.012.
- Motivation has a positive but not significant effect on employee performance with a path coefficient of 0.252 and a p-value of 0.234.
- Motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee career development with a path coefficient of 0.662 and a p-value of 0.000.
- Employee career development does not have a positive and significant effect on employee performance with a path coefficient of -0.041 and a p-value of 0.827.

1.16. Indirect Effect

Indirect effect analysis is useful for testing the hypothesis of the indirect effect of a variable that affects (exogenous) to the influenced variable (endogenous) mediated / mediated by the intervening variable. With the p-value criterion <0.05 , it is significant (the effect is not direct), meaning that the intervening variable plays a role in mediating the relationship between variables. If the p-value >0.05 is insignificant (the effect is direct), meaning that the intervening variable plays no role in mediating the relationship between variables.

Table 8 Specific Indirect Effect

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
MTV -> PK -> KK	0.059	0.184	0.129	0.209	0.184
GKD -> PK -> KK	0.189	0.061	0.029	0.135	0.026

Based on table 8. It can be concluded that:

The indirect effect of MTV -> PK -> KK is 0.059 (positive) with a p-value of $0.184 > 0.05$ (insignificant). This means that the variable Employee Career Development does not play a role in mediating the influence of motivation on employee performance of PT Hutama Karya Infrastruktur Pekanbaru-Padang Toll Road Development, Padang Sicinring Section.

The indirect effect of GKD -> PK -> KK is 0.189 (positive) with a p-value of $0.026 < 0.05$ (significant). This means that the variable Employee Career Development plays a role in mediating the influence of directive leadership style on employee performance of PT Hutama Karya Infrastruktur Pekanbaru-Padang Toll Road Development, Padang Sicinring Section.

The Directive Leadership Style variable has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with a p-value of $0.006 < 0.05$ and shows a t-statistical calculation of $0.391 > 0.164$. Thus, hypothesis 1 in the study is accepted.

The Directive Leadership Style variable has a positive and significant effect on Employee Career Development with a p-value of $0.012 < 0.05$ and shows a t-statistical calculation of $0.195 > 0.164$. Thus, hypothesis 2 in this study is accepted.

The Motivation variable has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with a p-value of $0.234 > 0.05$ and shows a t-statistical calculation of $0.252 > 0.164$. Thus, hypothesis 3 in this study was rejected.

Motivation The Motivation variable has a positive and significant effect on Employee Career Development with a p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$ and shows a t-statistical calculation of $0.662 > 0.164$. Thus, hypothesis 4 in the study was accepted.

Motivation Employee Career Development variables have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with a p-value of $0.827 > 0.05$ and show a t-statistical calculation of $-0.041 >$

0.164 . Thus, hypothesis 5 in this study is rejected.

Employee Career Development Variables do not play a role in mediating the influence of motivation on employee performance of PT Hutama Karya Infrastruktur Pekanbaru-Padang Toll Road Development, Padang Sicincin Section.

Employee Career Development Variables play a role in mediating the influence of directive leadership style on employee performance of PT Hutama Karya Infrastruktur Pekanbaru-Padang Toll Road Development, Padang Sicincin.

4. Conclusion

- The directive leadership style has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees of PT Hutama Karya Infrastruktur Pembangunan Tol Pekanbaru-Padang, Padang Sicincin.
- The directive leadership style has a positive and significant effect on the career development of employees of PT Hutama Karya Infrastruktur Pekanbaru-Padang Toll Road Development, Padang Sicincin Section.
- Motivation has a positive and but not significant effect on the performance of employees of PT Hutama Karya Infrastruktur Pekanbaru-Padang Toll Road Development, Padang Sicincin.
- Motivation has a positive and significant effect on the career development of employees of PT Hutama Karya Infrastruktur Pekanbaru-Padang Toll Road Development, Padang Sicincin Section.
- Employee career development does not have a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees of PT Hutama Karya Infrastruktur Pekanbaru-Padang Toll Road Development, Padang Sicincin Section.
- Employee Career Development does not play a role in mediating the influence of motivation on the performance of employees of PT Hutama Karya Infrastruktur Pekanbaru-Padang Toll Road Development, Padang Sicincin Section.
- Employee Career Development plays a role in mediating the influence of directive leadership style on employee performance of PT Hutama Karya Infrastruktur Pekanbaru-Padang Toll Road Development, Padang Sicincin Section.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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